

HOROSCOPE MATCHING IS BETTER THAN 10 STARS MATCHING IN MARRIAGE MATCHING

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Abstract:

Most of the astrologers have done marriage matching by only seeing dasavitha porutham. They satisfy only with dina porutham, gana porutham rajju porutham, mahendra porutha, shree deerga porutham, nadi porutham, rasi porutham, rasi lord porutham, yoni (sexual organ) porutham and vasiya porutham. But it is not enough. Apart from dasavitha porutham, horoscope Lagna, lagna lord and their standing star are very important.

Key Words: Marriage Matching, Dinam, Ganam, Rajju, Mahendram, Sthree Deergam, Nadi, Rasi, Rasi Lord, Yoni, Vasyam, Lagna, Lagna Lord, Standing Star, One Spouse, Two Spouse, More Than Two Spouse, Separation, Divorce.

Introduction:

When marriage life is happy, life is a paradise. But it is un happy, life will be a hell. So, marriage matching is very important for happy life. Apart from dasavitha porutham, lagna, lagna lord, sixth lord, twelfth lord, Mars, Venus and Jupiter's position are very important.

Daily Maching: It shows the happy life. Both husband and wife will enjoy the life very well if this matching is in their horoscope. It is calculated from the star of girl.

Gana Matching: There are three types of gana.

- Deva gana (divinely god)
- Human gana (normal people)
- Ratchasa gana (Saitan) This matching is very important to identify the natural character of the native.

Mahendra Matching: Really the name of this matching is Maha kendra (1, 4, 7, 10) matching. From this matching we should know the life of the couple and their children.

Sthree deergam Matching: This matching shows the husbands life span and indicates deerga sumangali yoga of the girl.

Yoni Matching: This matching indicates the pleasure from intercourse. It also tells the size of the sexual organs penis and vagina. Animals are used to explain the size.

Rasi Matching: This matching indicates the harmony between the husband and the wife . There is no rasi matching the couple would be separated by divorce.

Rasi Lord Matching: This matching indicates the understanding, between the couple's parents. It shows their parent's harmony.

Vasiya Matching: It indicates the attraction between the couple. It also shows the magnetic attraction of the couple, who is attracted by whom.

Rajju Matching: This matching indicates the life span of the husband. This matching is very very important. Stars are divided into five.

- Siro rajju (head)
- Kanda rajju (neck)
- Uthara rajju (abdomen)
- Ooru rajju (thigh)
- Patha rajju (feet)

This matching is must for marriage

- **Veda Matching:** This matching indicates the understanding of the couple every star has one vedai star (enemy star). We should avoid the vedai star in marriage matching.

38 Horoscope Matching (New Method using by me):

1. Matchings based by lagna	13
2. Matchings based by Moon	9
3. Shasta Ashtaga Matching	7
4. Comfort Matchings	3
5. Dasha Matchings	4
Total	36

We can see all this through example horoscopes:

Birth	Husband	Wife
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Date	02.08.1983	21.02.1986
Time	11.40 am	07.15. am
Place	Vellore	Vellore

	MOON	RAHU	MARS
	RASI OF HUSBAND		SUN
			VENUS MERCURY
	KETHU JUPITER	ASC SATURN	

	RAHU		MOON
VENUS JUPITER MERCURY ASC	RASI OF WIFE		
	SATURN MARS	KETHU	

Planet	Star	Star Lord
Lagna	Swathi 1	Rahu
Sun	Poosam 4	Saturn
Moon	Bharani 2	Venus
Mars	Punarvasu 3	Jupiter
Mercury	Magam 3	Kethu
Jupiter	Anusam 2	Saturn
Venus	Pooram 1	Venus
Saturn	Chitra 4	Mars
Rahu	Mirugasira 2	Mars
Kehu	Kettai 4	Mercury

Planet	Star	Star Lord
Lagna	Sathayam 4	Rahu
Sun	Sathayam 1	Rahu
Moon	Punarvasu 2	Jupiter
Mars	Kettai 1	Mercury
Mercury	Puratathi 2	Jupiter
Jupiter	Avittam 4	Mars
Venus	Sthayam 3	Rahu
Saturn	Anusam 4	Saturn
Rahu	Aswini 3	Kethu
Kehu	Swathi 1	Rahu

13 Matchings based by Lagna:

S.No	Lagna Matchings	Girl	Boy	Result
1.	Lagna – Lagna	Aquaris	Libra	Best
2	Lagna Lord	Saturn 10	Venus	Best
3	Lagna Lord place	10	11	Best
4	Lagna Lord in others horoscope	1(10)	1(11)	Medium
5	Lagna star Lord	Jupiter	Mars	Medium
6	Lagna star Lord place	10(1)3	11(9)8	Medium
7	Lagna star Lord in others horoscope	1(10)3	1(2)8	Worst
8	Lagna 7 th Lord	Sun	Mars	Best
9	Lagna 7 th Lord Place	1	9	Best
10	Lagna 7 th Lord in others horoscope	10	10	Medium
11	7 th Lord Standing star	Rahu	Saturn	Medium
12	7 th Lord place	3	2(1)	Worst
13	7 th Lord in others horoscope.	1(10)	8	Worst

9 Matchings based by Moon:

S.No	Moon Matchings	Girl	Boy	Result
1.	Moon Standing Star	Jupiter	Venus	Worst
2	Moon Star Lord place	9	5	Worst
3	Moon Star Lord in others horoscope	10	9	Worst
4	Moon's 7 th Lord	Jupiter	Venus	Worst
5	Moon's 7 th Lord Place	9	11	Worst
6	Moon's 7 th Lord in others horoscope	6	5	Medium
7	Moon's 7 th Lords star	Mars	Venus	Medium
8	Moon's 7 th Lord star's place	6	5	Medium
9	Moon's 7 th Lord star in Others horoscope.	9	3	Medium

7 Shasta Ashtaga Matchings:

S.No	Shasta Matchings	Girl	Boy	Result
1.	Lagna Lord	4 - 10	3 - 11	Medium
2	Lagna star Lord	4 - 10	3 - 11	Worst
3	Lagna 7 th Lord	4 – 10	2 – 12	Medium
4	7 th Lord's star Lord	3 – 11	2 – 7	Worst
5	Moon Star Lord	1	4 – 10	Medium
6	Moon's 7 th Lord	1	4 – 10	Medium
7	Moon's 7 th Lords star Lord	4 – 10	3 - 11	Best

3 Comfort Matchings:

S.No	Comfort Matching	Girl	Boy	Result
1	Mars – Venus conjunction Girls mars in Boys Rasi	1 – 10	3 – 11	Best
	Boys Venus in Girls Rasi	4 – 10	4 – 10	Best
2	3/7/11 and 12	Rahu 3	3/7/11/12 Lords hidden	Worst
3	Jupiter and 5 th Lord	5 th Lord with Jupiter	Saturn exhaltation	Best

4 Dosha Matchings:

S.No	Dosha Matching	Girl	Boy	Result
1	Rahu, Kethu Dosha	3 /9 Nil	2/8 Yes.	Worst
2	Mars Dosha	Nil	Nil	Best
3	6/7/8 Empty	Ok	Planets in 7, 8	Worst
4	Dosa Santhi	Mild	Mild	Medium

Final Result (Consolidation):

Total Best	9	25%
Total Medium	14	39%
Total Worst	13	36%
Total	36	100%

Worst dominates than best here:

So, there is no matching. If they have married, they would have been separated

Conclusion:

The world of science and technology is always updated Astrology is also science. So, we should update ourselves. 36 matchings is very best to calculated the real result of marriage matching.

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